

Electoral Management Body and Challenges of Elections in Nigeria Fourth Republic

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Abstract

This research explores the role of Electoral Management Bodies (EMBs), particularly the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), in ensuring free and fair elections in the Nigeria Fourth Republic. Over two decades of uninterrupted democratic rule in Nigeria's Fourth Republic, the conduct of free and fair elections remains a persistent challenge. Electoral processes in Nigeria have often been marred by irregularities such as vote-buying, voter suppression, ballot stuffing, and post-election violence. This seminar adopted a descriptive contextual analysis to explore the institutional framework, operational challenges, reforms, and the impact of electoral practices on the democratic process in Nigeria. The contextual analysis method involves examining the electoral framework, historical election data, government policies, and stakeholder interactions. This method allows for a comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics that influence electoral integrity in Nigeria. Data for this seminar was sourced from publications of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), reports from international election observers, and scholarly articles on electoral processes in Nigeria. It also highlights the successes and failures of INEC in conducting credible elections while proposing solutions to improve the transparency and efficiency of future electoral processes. Findings revealed that one of the significant challenges faced by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in Nigeria is political interference, which has hampered its ability to conduct free, fair, and credible elections. It was recommended that for Nigeria to consolidate its democracy, further reforms are necessary to enhance the independence and effectiveness of INEC.

Keywords: Electoral Management Bodies, Free and Fair Elections, Nigeria, Fourth Republic, INEC, Electoral Reform

Introduction

The electoral process is essential for strengthening democracy, and the contribution of electoral management bodies (EMBs) in guaranteeing elections that are free, fair, and trustworthy is immensely important. In Nigeria, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) plays a pivotal role in managing elections in the Fourth Republic. This research examines the role of INEC and its effectiveness in ensuring electoral integrity, amidst several challenges such as political interference, logistical issues, and voter apathy. The focus of the study is on understanding the evolution of INEC's functions and reforms to guarantee free and fair elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. Elections are a critical cornerstone of democratic governance, providing citizens with the opportunity to choose their representatives and influence government policy. These institutions, known as Electoral Management Bodies (EMBs), play a vital role in safeguarding the democratic process. In Nigeria, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) serves as the primary EMB, responsible for organizing and conducting elections in the Fourth Republic, which began in 1999 after decades of military rule.

The shift to civilian governance in 1999 initiated the Fourth Republic, a significant chapter in Nigeria's political development. Since that time, Nigeria has held numerous elections across federal, state, and local levels. Nevertheless, many of these elections have faced accusations of irregularities, electoral violence, voter suppression, and result manipulation (Onapajo, 2014). In response to these issues, INEC has implemented various reforms to enhance the electoral process and better ensure that election outcomes truly represent the people's choices (Ibeanu, 2007). The effectiveness of these reforms has been mixed, with some elections recognized for their credibility most notably the 2015 presidential election, which was historic as the first instance of an incumbent president losing re-election in Nigeria (Adigun, 2016).

Election witnessed so far itemize

The concept of free and fair elections is integral to democratic consolidation. According to Elklit and Svensson (1997), an election can be considered free and fair when it is conducted in a transparent manner. In Nigeria, this ideal has often been difficult to achieve due to structural weaknesses in the electoral system, logistical challenges, and political interference (Omotola, 2013). However, INEC has made progress through technological innovations such as biometric voter registration and electronic transmission of results (Orji & Uwalaka, 2016).

The Electoral processes in Nigeria have often been marred by irregularities such as vote-buying, voter suppression, ballot stuffing, and post-election violence (Onapajo, 2014). While the (INEC) has implemented several reforms aimed at improving the credibility of elections, including the adoption of biometric voter registration and the electronic transmission of results (Orji & Uwalaka, 2016), questions about the transparency and fairness of the electoral process still linger. INEC, which is constitutionally mandated to manage elections and ensure their credibility, often faces challenges related to its independence and capacity to resist political pressure. Despite constitutional guarantees, allegations of political interference in the appointment and functioning of INEC's officials persist, raising concerns about the body's ability to function as an impartial arbiter in the electoral process (Ojo, 2019). The lack of full independence erodes public trust and creates perceptions of bias in favor of the ruling political elites (Onapajo, 2014).

Logistical challenges also present a major issue in ensuring free and fair elections. Nigeria's vast and diverse geography, coupled with its infrastructure deficits, make it difficult for INEC to distribute electoral materials and personnel efficiently, especially to rural and conflict-prone areas. This often leads to delays, missing materials, and poorly coordinated elections. For instance, the postponement of the 2019 general elections due to logistical problems at the eleventh hour raised serious questions about INEC's preparedness and capacity to manage elections effectively (Kew & Akinrinde, 2020).

In addition to logistical and administrative challenges, electoral fraud and violence have become almost endemic to Nigeria's electoral processes. Vote-buying, underage voting, and the manipulation of results have been recurring problems, with political actors often deploying thugs to intimidate voters and disrupt polling units. Despite efforts by INEC to improve election security and transparency, such electoral malpractice remains pervasive (Lewis, 2008; Nwokeke, 2019). Moreover, electoral violence, both during and after elections, undermines the credibility of the process, with many Nigerians expressing apathy and declining participation due to fears of violence and a lack of faith in the system (YIAGA Africa, 2021). The electoral process is crucial in conferring legitimacy on the elected government, and without credible elections, democratic consolidation remains elusive (Dahl, 1998). Additionally, international observers and organizations have continuously highlighted these challenges in Nigeria's elections, pointing to the need for deeper structural reforms within INEC and the broader electoral framework (European Union Election Observation Mission, 2019).

This study examines the role of INEC in the Fourth Republic, focusing on its contributions to the conduct of free and fair elections. It also analyzes the major challenges the commission has faced, including political interference, logistical issues, and voter apathy. Furthermore, this research assesses the impact of electoral reforms, such as the 2022 Electoral Act (Ugochukwu, 2023), and proposes strategies to strengthen electoral management in Nigeria. The central argument of this paper is that while INEC has made significant strides in improving the credibility of elections, more reforms are necessary to ensure that future elections are genuinely free, fair, and transparent. In response to these problems, this research seeks to critically examine the role of INEC in ensuring free and fair elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. Specifically, it will analyze the institutional challenges facing INEC, assess the effectiveness of recent reforms, and propose solutions aimed at enhancing the credibility of future elections. While reforms such as the introduction of the Smart Card Reader and the 2022 Electoral Act have made some progress in improving electoral transparency, the persistence of logistical inefficiencies, political interference, and electoral fraud indicates that further work is needed (Ugochukwu, 2023).

Free and Fair Elections

Elections are crucial pillars of democracy, providing a legitimate means for citizens to choose their leaders and hold them accountable. For elections to fulfill this role, they must meet the standards of being free and fair. The terms "free" and "fair" have distinct yet interrelated meanings in the context of elections, each involving specific criteria and standards recognized globally by electoral bodies, civil society, and international organizations. Free elections are those in which all eligible citizens have the right and opportunity to participate in the electoral process without undue restrictions or coercion. Freedom in elections refers to the conditions under which voters can express their preferences without fear of reprisal, manipulation, or external pressure (Schedler, 2002). A free election ensures that:

- **Voter participation:** Citizens are free to register as voters and cast their ballots in a peaceful and conducive environment, without intimidation or hindrance.
- **Candidate freedom:** Political parties and candidates must be allowed to organize, campaign, and present their programs to the electorate without undue restriction or interference from the state or other actors.

- **Freedom of expression:** Voters, candidates, and media must be able to express opinions, share information, and campaign freely. There must be no censorship, media harassment, or punitive measures for political expression (Norris, 2014).

Fair elections ensure that the process, from voter registration to vote counting, is transparent, impartial, and devoid of manipulation or fraud. Fairness in elections addresses both the equal treatment of all political participants and the integrity of the electoral process. For an election to be considered fair, it must adhere to the following criteria (Birch, 2011):

- **Impartial electoral administration:** The election must be conducted by a neutral and independent electoral body. (Elklit & Reynolds, 2005). In Nigeria, for example, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) is tasked with ensuring impartiality in the electoral process (Ibeanu, 2015).
- **Equal suffrage:** All eligible citizens should have equal voting rights, and the electoral system should ensure that every vote has equal value.
- **Transparency in procedures:** Electoral procedures, such as voter registration, vote counting, and the announcement of results, must be conducted openly to allow scrutiny by observers, political parties, and the public.
- **Access to legal recourse:** In cases of electoral malpractice, there must be mechanisms for challenging results or addressing grievances through legal or administrative channels. This includes the availability of election tribunals or courts where disputes can be fairly adjudicated.

Evolution of the Electoral Management Body in Nigeria

Nigeria's electoral history has been characterized by periods of military rule, electoral malpractice, and political instability. The establishment of INEC in 1998 marked a significant shift toward institutionalizing democracy in Nigeria's Fourth Republic (Ibeanu, 2007). The Fourth Republic began in 1999 with the transition to civilian rule, and since then, INEC has overseen several election cycles, including the presidential elections of 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, and 2019. The evolution of Electoral Management Bodies (EMBs) in Nigeria reflects the country's political history, spanning colonial rule, military dictatorship, and the ongoing democratic experiment in the Fourth Republic. The management of elections in Nigeria has historically been fraught with challenges, from a lack of independence to political manipulation, but gradual reforms have shaped the current framework, with

the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) as the focal institution overseeing elections today.

Colonial and Post-Colonial Periods (1950s-1960s)

The concept of an Electoral Management Body in Nigeria dates back to the colonial period, particularly in the 1950s, when Nigeria prepared for self-government. The first elections in the country were organized under the supervision of colonial administrators with no independent electoral institution. However, the British colonial government established the Electoral Commission of Nigeria (ECN) in 1959 to conduct elections leading up to Nigeria's independence in 1960 (Kurfi, 2005). Despite some early criticisms, the ECN laid the foundation for organized electoral processes in Nigeria. After independence, the ECN continued to manage elections, including the controversial 1964 general elections and the 1965 Western Region elections, both of which were characterized by violence and allegations of manipulation (Ayoade, 1983). The failures of these elections contributed to the political instability that culminated in the military coup of 1966, marking the beginning of a series of military regimes that would dominate Nigeria's political landscape for decades.

Military Era (1966-1999)

During the years of military rule, Nigeria's electoral institutions were repeatedly restructured as the military regimes oscillated between organizing elections to legitimize their rule and outright suspending democratic processes. In 1978, under General Olusegun Obasanjo's military government, the Federal Electoral Commission (FEDECO) was established to organize elections as part of the transition to civilian rule. FEDECO oversaw the 1979 elections, which led to the Second Republic under President Shehu Shagari (Jinadu, 1997). However, the 1983 elections, which FEDECO also supervised, were widely criticized for electoral fraud, violence, and vote rigging, leading to another military coup. General Muhammadu Buhari's military, which took power after the coup, dissolved FEDECO, and Nigeria entered another period of military dictatorship.

In 1987, General Ibrahim Babangida's regime established the National Electoral Commission (NEC) as part of a renewed effort towards transition to democracy. The NEC was responsible for overseeing the controversial 1993 presidential election, which was annulled by Babangida's regime after it was widely believed that Moshood Abiola had won. This annulment led to political unrest and

further damaged public trust in the electoral process (Momoh, 2000). Following Babangida's resignation, the National Electoral Commission of Nigeria (NECON) was created under General Sani Abacha's regime in 1995, but it did not organize any credible elections before Abacha's sudden death in 1998. The repeated restructuring of EMBs during the military era reflected the regimes' need to control electoral outcomes, undermining the independence and credibility of electoral institutions (Ibrahim, 2007).

The Fourth Republic and the Establishment of INEC (1999-Present)

Nigeria's return to democracy in 1999, following General Abdulsalami Abubakar's transitional government, marked a significant turning point in the evolution of the country's progress. The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) was established in 1998 by the 1999 Constitution, replacing NECON. INEC was tasked with organizing the first elections of the Fourth Republic in 1999, which resulted in the election of General Olusegun Obasanjo as president (Omotola, 2020). Since its creation, INEC has overseen six general elections—1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, and 2019 with varying degrees of success and credibility. The 2003 and 2007 elections were marred by widespread irregularities, leading to public outcry and international criticism (Lewis, 2021). However, under the leadership of Professor Attahiru Jega, INEC made significant strides in improving the credibility of elections, particularly with the introduction of biometric voter registration and the Smart Card Reader for the 2015 elections (Ibeanu, 2015). The 2015 election, which saw the peaceful transition of power from President Goodluck Jonathan to the opposition candidate Muhammadu Buhari, was hailed as a watershed moment in Nigeria's democratic development (Adigun, 2016). INEC continues to play a central role in Nigeria's electoral process, but it faces ongoing challenges such as political interference, logistical inefficiencies, and electoral violence. The commission's adoption of the 2022 Electoral Act, which includes provisions for electronic transmission of results and improved election security, represents a new phase in INEC's evolution as it seeks to address the persistent issues plaguing Nigeria's elections (Ugochukwu, 2023).

Recent Reforms and Current Challenges

One of the major reforms in recent years was the passage of the 2022 Electoral Act, which introduced several changes aimed at enhancing transparency and credibility in the electoral process.

These reforms have been praised by local and international observers as a step in the right direction, but the success of their implementation remains to be seen in future elections. Despite the reforms, INEC continues to face significant challenges. Political interference, influence of money in politics, and the threat of violence during elections remain substantial obstacles to the conduct of free and fair elections in Nigeria (YIAGA Africa, 2021).

Electoral Management in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

Electoral management refers to the processes, institutions, and frameworks that ensure the effective organization and conduct of elections. In Nigeria's Fourth Republic, which began in 1999, electoral management has been a critical aspect of the country's transition to and consolidation of democracy. The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) is the body constitutionally mandated to oversee the electoral process and ensure the conduct of free, fair, and credible elections. However, the management of elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic has faced numerous challenges.

1. Establishment of INEC in the Fourth Republic

The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) was established by the 1999 Constitution, following the dissolution of its predecessor, the National Electoral Commission of Nigeria (NECON). The 1999 Constitution vested INEC with the responsibility of organizing and supervising elections in Nigeria, including presidential, gubernatorial, National Assembly, and State Assembly elections (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999). INEC's core mandate is to ensure that elections are conducted in a manner that promotes democracy, fairness, and the rule of law.

INEC is tasked with several functions, including voter registration, delimitation of electoral constituencies, regulation of political parties, and the monitoring of election finances. Since its establishment, INEC has undergone various reforms aimed at enhancing its capacity and independence, particularly in response to the numerous challenges it has faced in delivering credible elections (Omotola, 2020).

2. Challenges in Electoral Management

Despite significant progress since its establishment, INEC has struggled with several challenges in electoral management during the Fourth Republic. These challenges have undermined the credibility of elections and, by extension, the legitimacy of elected governments. Some of the major challenges include:

- **Electoral Violence:** Electoral violence has been a recurring issue in Nigeria, particularly during the 2007 and 2011 elections. Violence has manifested in various forms, including intimidation of voters, attacks on political opponents, and clashes between supporters of rival parties (Nwolise, 2017).
- **Voter Registration and Logistics:** The management of voter registration has been a significant challenge for INEC, particularly in terms of ensuring the accuracy and completeness of the voters' register. In the early elections of the Fourth Republic, there were widespread complaints of voter disenfranchisement due to faulty registration processes and missing names on the register (Ibeanu, 2015). Furthermore, logistical challenges such as the late arrival of election materials and the failure of card readers have hindered the smooth conduct of elections (Orji & Uwalaka, 2016).
- **Election Technology:** The introduction of technology, such as the biometric voter registration (BVR) system and the Smart Card Reader, was aimed at curbing electoral fraud, especially issues like multiple voting and underage voting. However, the use of technology in Nigerian elections has faced significant operational and technical challenges. During the 2015 and 2019 elections, there were reports of malfunctioning card readers, which led to delays in the voting process and in some cases, the use of manual accreditation of voters (Agbaje & Adejumobi, 2021).

Electoral Reforms and Progress

Since 1999, several reforms have been introduced to improve electoral management in Nigeria. These reforms have focused on strengthening the independence of INEC, enhancing voter registration processes, and introducing technological innovations to reduce electoral malpractice. One of the most notable reforms was the introduction of the Electoral Act of 2022, which significantly amended the previous electoral laws to address emerging challenges in the electoral process (Electoral Act, 2022). Key provisions in the 2022 Electoral Act include the electronic transmission of election results, which aims to enhance transparency and reduce the likelihood of result manipulation during collation. This reform was widely praised during the 2023 general elections, as it helped to build public confidence in the integrity of the electoral process (Nwokeke, 2023).

Cases of Elections in the Fourth Republic

The 2007 presidential election in Nigeria was a watershed moment in the country's electoral history, as it marked the first civilian-to-civilian transition in the Fourth Republic. However, the election is widely regarded as one of the most controversial and poorly conducted in Nigeria's democratic history, characterized by widespread irregularities, violence, and allegations of electoral fraud (Adetula, 2018). The election raised serious concerns about the ability of Nigeria's electoral management body, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), to conduct free and fair elections.

Overview of the 2007 Presidential Election in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

The 2007 presidential election was held on April 21, 2007. The election saw Umaru Musa Yar'Adua of the ruling People's Democratic Party (PDP) emerge victorious with 24.6 million votes, representing approximately 70% of the total votes cast (Omotola, 2020). His closest rival, Muhammadu Buhari of the All Nigeria Peoples Party (ANPP), received 6.6 million votes (19%), while Atiku Abubakar of the Action Congress (AC) came in third with 2.6 million votes (7%) (European Union Election Observation Mission, 2017). The election was significant because it represented the first time a sitting president, Olusegun Obasanjo, would hand over power to another civilian president. However, the process was fraught with major irregularities, and both local and international observers condemned the election as deeply flawed (Ibrahim, 2007).

Overview of the 2015 Presidential Election in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

1. The 2015 presidential election was highly competitive, with Muhammadu Buhari, a former military ruler, contesting the election for the fourth time, against Goodluck Jonathan, who had been in power since 2010 following the death of President Umaru Musa Yar'Adua. Buhari's victory, with 15.4 million votes (53.96% of the total), was a historic moment, as it marked the first time an opposition candidate had won a presidential election in Nigeria. Jonathan, who garnered 12.8 million votes (44.96%), graciously conceded defeat, which helped to ensure a peaceful transition (INEC, 2015). **Key Features of the 2015 Election** are Introduction of the Permanent Voter Card (PVC) and Card Reader Technology, Postponement of the Election, Peace Accord and the Role of Civil Society and Electoral Transparency and Credibility.

Overview of the 2019 Presidential Election in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

1. The 2019 election was initially scheduled for February 16 but was postponed by a week just hours before the polls were set to open. The Independent National Electoral Commission

(INEC) cited logistical challenges as the reason for the postponement, including the late delivery of sensitive electoral materials (INEC, 2019). Despite the delay, the election eventually went ahead, with over 84 million registered voters and 72 presidential candidates vying for the presidency. Muhammadu Buhari was declared the winner, securing 15.2 million votes (55.60%) to Atiku Abubakar's 11.3 million votes (41.22%) (INEC, 2019). **Key Features of the 2019 Presidential Election** are Logistical Challenges and Postponement, Voter Turnout and Apathy, Security and Electoral Violence and Allegations of Electoral Fraud and Irregularities.

Challenges Faced by INEC

Political Interference

One of the significant challenges faced by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in Nigeria is political interference, which has hampered its ability to conduct free, fair, and credible elections. Political interference refers to the undue influence exerted by political actors or government officials over the operations of INEC. This interference can take various forms, including attempts to influence the appointment of INEC officials, manipulation of the electoral process, and pressure to alter election results.

Logistical and Security Issues Faced by INEC

Logistical and security challenges are among the most persistent issues faced by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in Nigeria. These issues can significantly affect the efficiency and credibility of the electoral process. In many cases, they lead to election postponements, disenfranchisement of voters, electoral violence, and general distrust in the electoral system.

Logistical Challenges

1. **Delayed Distribution of Electoral Materials:** One of the most common logistical issues is the delayed distribution of electoral materials to polling units across the country. Due to the size and diversity of Nigeria, INEC often faces challenges in delivering sensitive electoral materials such as ballot papers, result sheets, and card readers to remote areas.
2. **Inadequate Technology and Infrastructure:** Despite efforts to introduce technology into Nigeria's electoral system, including the use of smart card readers for voter accreditation, technological challenges have continued to affect elections. Failures in card readers, poor internet connectivity in rural areas, and insufficient backup mechanisms often result in delays,

disenfranchisement of voters, and the extension of voting hours or days (YIAGA Africa, 2019). These issues undermine the credibility of the elections and fuel allegations of malpractice.

3. **Training and Capacity of Electoral Officers** Another logistical issue concerns the training and capacity of electoral officials. Many ad-hoc staff recruited to assist in conducting elections, such as university graduates and members of the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC), are often insufficiently trained on how to operate electoral technology or handle sensitive electoral tasks. This lack of adequate preparation has resulted in procedural errors, delays in voting, and challenges during result collation (Okoye, 2020).
4. **Election Postponements** Election postponements have become a recurrent issue in Nigeria's elections due to logistical problems. In addition to the 2019 elections, the 2011 and 2015 general elections also faced postponements due to INEC's inability to complete logistical arrangements in time (Alabi, 2020). These postponements cause voter confusion, dampen electoral enthusiasm, and sometimes fuel suspicions of manipulation by political actors.

Security Issues

1. **Electoral Violence** Electoral violence is a major security issue in Nigerian elections, affecting both voters and INEC officials. Violence often erupts during the campaign period, on election day, or in the aftermath of election results, especially in politically volatile regions. The 2019 general election witnessed several incidents of violence, particularly in states like Rivers, Lagos, and Kano, where political thugs attacked polling units, snatched ballot boxes, and intimidated voters (Human Rights Watch, 2019). Electoral violence deters voter participation and can lead to the cancellation or suspension of elections in affected areas.
2. **Insecurity in Conflict Zones** The rise of insurgency, banditry, and other forms of violent conflict in various parts of Nigeria poses significant security challenges to the electoral process. In regions affected by Boko Haram in the Northeast, for example, insecurity has made it difficult for INEC to set up polling units or ensure the safety of electoral officers and voters (Vanguard, 2019). Additionally, armed groups and militias have increasingly targeted electoral officials and disrupted elections to undermine democratic processes.
3. **Threats to INEC Personnel** INEC personnel, including ad-hoc staff, are frequently targeted by political thugs, insurgent groups, and criminal elements during elections. The deployment of INEC officials to volatile areas often comes with significant risks, including physical attacks

and kidnapping. During the 2019 general election, there were reports of INEC officials being attacked in various states, resulting in the suspension of voting in some polling units (YIAGA Africa, 2019).

4. **Lack of Adequate Security Personnel** Another security issue is the lack of adequate security personnel to manage the large number of polling units across the country. While the Nigerian Police Force is primarily responsible for securing polling stations, there are often not enough officers to provide comprehensive coverage, particularly in rural and high-risk areas. This gap in security coverage can lead to the intimidation of voters and the manipulation of results (Okoye, 2020).

Impact of logistical and security issues on the Electoral Process are Voter Apathy and Disenfranchisement, Delayed and Disputed Election Results and Undermining Electoral Credibility.

Conclusion

The role of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) is critical to the conduct of free and fair elections in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. Despite the challenges faced by the body, INEC has made significant strides in ensuring electoral integrity through reforms and innovations. However, political interference, logistical difficulties, and a lack of public trust remain significant challenges. For Nigeria to consolidate its democracy, further reforms are necessary to enhance the independence and effectiveness of INEC.

Recommendations

1. The appointment of INEC officials should be made more transparent and based on recommendations from an independent body, such as a Judicial or Electoral Reform Committee. Additionally, INEC's financial autonomy should be guaranteed through the direct allocation of funds from the Consolidated Revenue Fund, as opposed to relying on the executive branch for its budget.
2. Strengthening the legal frameworks governing INEC's operations is essential for protecting its independence. A review of the 2010 Electoral Act and subsequent amendments is necessary to introduce new clauses that empower INEC to act independently without undue influence from the executive or legislature.

3. Strengthening INEC's institutional capacity is another key aspect of ensuring its independence. This includes providing adequate resources, training, and technological tools to enable INEC to carry out its duties effectively.

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